

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING ROLEPLAY TECHNIQUES IN DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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*“All the world's a stage, and all the men and women merely players;
They have their exits and their entrances, and one man
in his time plays many parts, his acts being seven ages.”*

William Shakespeare

Annotation: In this article will discuss about effectiveness of using roleplay techniues in developing communicative competence.

Keywords: effectiveness, role-play techniques, communicative competence, EFL Learners.

As an international language, English has become the most important language that should be mastered by all people from different countries. The basic purpose of learning English is to use and communicate the language as a human communication tool.

This paper will discuss the significance of communicative competence relative to the field of college English education and explore an enjoyable way to increase students' intercultural awareness, sensitivity, and knowledge through collaborative, group-generated role plays. Role-play is the typical social communicative activity within a communicative approach. The rationales of communicative approach direct that composing and manipulating meaningful role-play activities within the framework of English classroom to cultivate students' communicative competence is of vital importance. Within this pedagogical framework and methodology, small teams of students create characters, develop a story, write dialogues, and perform extended role plays based on various intercultural situations. This technique utilizes an active process of communicative pre-writing tasks, multidraft scripts, rehearsal, self-direction, performance, and peer feedback. This long-term process allows learners to develop expressive intercultural language skills which improve

communicative competence and broaden international sensitivity. Take Family Album U.S.A. class performance as an example, the following will focus on extended role plays and how they could provide learners with an opportunity to develop overall communicative competence.

Role-play is considered one of the most effective teaching and learning techniques in the 21 st century. In the field of education, role-play can be defined and explained in different ways. Firstly, role-playing is a special method by which learners can become different characters to communicate in new situations. In this case, Ladousse (1987) argued that “when students assume a “Role”, they play a part (either their own or somebody else) in a specific situation. “Play” means that it is taken on in a safe environment in which students are as joyful as possible. It is a teaching method in which students are given specific roles and they need to speak and behave based on the roles they receive. Moreover, Saglamel and Kayaoglu (2013) stated that role-play is a drama activity that allows learners to express themselves in creative ways that could be different from their identity. It is an effective technique to develop students’ speaking skills as it provides students with an opportunity to take roles of different persons in real-life situations. Therefore, this technique is really important in teaching speaking because it gives students the opportunity to practice communicating in different social contexts.

Role play is defined as the projection in real life situations with social activities. In this activity, students play different roles in a particular language scene to solve the practical problems they may encounter, and use of language, movement, facial expressions and other means to act out what happened in that scene. Meanwhile, the full performance of activities can be an active classroom atmosphere, mobilize the enthusiasm of the students. The detailed teaching of role play is categorized into three steps: presentation, comprehension, consolidation and utilization. For a long story, a teacher usually postpones the third step to the second teaching class. In the process of presentation, a teacher acts as an conductor to give students a whole idea about the story by various means, such as, multi-media power point. Usually such kinds of vivid ways grasp the students’ attention deeply. In the process of comprehension, a

teacher checks if the students understand the content of teaching by questions. In the third step, students participate in the communicational dialogue and role play. In this process, the students play as dominant actors organized by the teacher. So students can practice English in the following ways: perform the original dialogues in the texts or revised ones, illustration and presentation, repetition paragraph by paragraph, theatric performance, and revised English songs etc. Role playing activities are not simple fun games but communicatively interactive classroom activity with the learners as the center of learning and with task as the central part.

Within a creative, communicative, and collaborative setting, role plays benefit learners in many ways. Students can be exposed to an incredibly wide variety of experiences and potential experiences while improving overall communicative competence. Structures, functions, and the vocabulary necessary for dealing with these situations may be introduced and exercised in a realistic and meaningful way. Role plays provide training for both speaking and listening in any language-learning situation. Role plays are an essential dress rehearsal which enables learners to do more than learn a set of phrases as they will experience how communication and interaction might take place in a variety of situations.

Roleplays provide learners with the opportunity to examine, understand, and acquire knowledge which will assist and better facilitate intercultural communication. This type of creative, communicative task will provide an opportunity for experimentation with language and experimenting with knowledge about various cultures. Learning from peers through group activities will benefit students implicitly and explicitly. Within this framework, a higher level of communicative competence and a broader understanding of intercultural exchange may be obtained.

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